

CAREC Free Trade Agreement Guidelines

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31 Jan 2022

Draft Public Consultation

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

ADB	Asian Development Bank
APEC	Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation
ARIC	Asia Regional Integration Center
CAREC	Central Asia Regional Economic Cooperation
CER	Closer Economic Relations between Australia and New Zealand
CITA	CAREC Integrated Trade Agenda
CPTPP	Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific
CTS	Consolidated Tariff Schedule
DDA	Doha Development Agenda
EAEU	Eurasian Economic Union
EBRD	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EVSL	Early Voluntary Sectoral Liberalization
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment
FTA	Free Trade Agreement
GATS	General Agreement on Trade in Services
GATT	General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade
GPTAD	Global Preferential Trade Agreements Database
GSP	Generalized System of Preferences
GVC	Global Value Chain
IDB	Integrated Data Base
IMF	International Monetary Fund
IsDB	Islamic Development Bank
ITA	International Trade Administration
MFN	Most Favored Nation
NAFTA	North America Free Trade Area
NTM	Non-tariff measures
PTA	Preferential Trade Agreement
RCEP	Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership
RTA	Regional Trade Agreement
SPS	Sanitary and Phytosanitary
TAIEX	Technical Assistance and Information Exchange
TBT	Technical Barriers to Trade
TFA	Trade Facilitation Agreement
TPP	Trans Pacific Partnership
TTIP	Transatlantic Trade and Investment Partnership
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNSD	United Nations Statistical Division
WCO	World Customs Organization
WITS	World Integrated Trade Solutions
WTO	World Trade Organization

Key Terms

Accession	Becoming a member of the WTO, signing on to its agreements
Anti-dumping duties	GATT's Article 6 allows anti-dumping duties to be imposed on goods that are deemed to be dumped and causing injury to producers of competing products in the importing country. These duties are equal to the difference between the goods' export price and their normal value, if dumping causes injury
Applied tariff/rates	Duties that are charged on imports which can be below the bound rates
Countervailing measures	Action taken by the importing country, usually in the form of increased duties to offset subsidies given to producers or exporters in the exporting country
Customs union	Members apply a common external tariff
Enabling Clause	This refers to the 1979 Decision on Differential and More Favourable Treatment, Reciprocity and Fuller Participation of Developing Countries
Free trade area	Trade within the group is duty free but members set their own tariffs on imports from non-members
G7	Group of seven leading industrial countries: Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, United Kingdom, United States
Intellectual property rights	Ownership of ideas, including literary and artistic works (protected by copyright), inventions (protected by patents), signs for distinguishing goods of an enterprise (protected by trademarks) and other elements of industrial property
Multilateral	Involving all members in the WTO context
Most favored nation (MFN) tariff	Normal non-discriminatory tariff charged on imports (excludes preferential tariffs under free trade agreements and other schemes or tariffs charged inside quotas)
Noodle/Spaghetti bowl effect	A proliferation of free trade agreements between individual countries
Preferential trade agreements	Trade preferences, such as lower or zero tariffs, which a member may offer to a trade partner unilaterally
Regional trade agreements	Reciprocal trade agreements between two or more partners to liberalize tariffs and services. They include free trade areas and customs unions and economic integration agreements on services
Rules of origin	Laws, regulations and administrative procedures which determine a product's country of origin
Sanitary and phytosanitary measures (SPS)	Measures dealing with food safety and animal and plant health. Sanitary: for human and animal health. Phytosanitary: for plants and plant products
Sensitive sectors	Sectors for which the tariffs remain positive within the FTAs
Tariff	Customs duties on merchandise imports
WTO+	Commitments building on those already agreed to by WTO members, e.g. a further reduction in tariffs
WTO-x	Commitments dealing with issues going beyond the current WTO mandate, e.g. on e-commerce

1. Executive Summary

These guidelines draw upon consultations conducted virtually with CAREC country officials, ADB staff, various stakeholders including the CAREC Institute, and desk research. CAREC economies have been increasing their integration with the region through expansion in their trade and investment links. Ongoing improvements in connectivity through physical infrastructure are reducing transport costs, creating opportunities for dramatic improvements in livelihoods and securing a basis for long term prosperity. Policy reforms are required to allow countries in the region to take full advantage of these improvements in physical infrastructure. If designed carefully to meet the disparate needs of its members, a CAREC-wide FTA can provide the complementary soft infrastructure to increase trade and investment and assist in diversifying and modernizing economies of the region to achieve more inclusive growth. Such a design should ensure compatibility and coherence with other bilateral, regional, and multilateral agreements, as well as cross-cutting issues within each country's national reform agenda.

Participation in GVCs based on ever finer specialization along fragmented supply chains and the rapid rise of e-commerce and role of data over the last two decades as facilitators of efficient GVCs have created pressures for common rules and norms on topics that were not considered when the WTO was established in 1995 (Pomfret, 2020a). The task of avoiding a “noodle bowl” of conflicting standards that increase the complexity of international trade would ideally be handled by a multilateral agency with global membership, but the issues do not fit well with the WTO's consensus requirement and there is no other satisfactory forum for setting common universal standards on new trade-relevant matters.

Trade-related regional integration is no longer mainly about promoting intra-regional trade behind barriers to external trade; it is much more about regional cooperation to improve competitiveness in world markets. The significance of tariffs has declined substantially, as countries reduce trade barriers so that producers can access world-best inputs. Countries wishing to push WTO rules further (WTO+) or into new areas (WTO-X) have been blocked by the need for consensus. Consensus is a straitjacket because a substantial number of WTO members are on the wrong side of the digital divide and many countries do not participate in GVCs; WTO members in these two overlapping groups are unconvinced of the need for reform and block change.¹ Institutional arrangements for countries wanting to push agreement further or into new areas have varied from deeper regional or bilateral agreements to “mega-regionals” that are to varying degrees “open”. The difficulty with this approach is that it may lead to conflicting regulatory standards across different negotiating blocs (a noodle bowl effect), even if inadvertently through differences in detail, which would be incompatible with the vision of GVCs that have a global reach in identifying participants.

¹ A WTO option could be plurilateral agreements like the 1997 Information Technology Agreement (ITA) whose signatories commit to eliminating MFN tariffs on IT products covered by the Agreement. The number of participants has grown to 82, representing about 97 per cent of world trade in IT products, and in December 2015 over 50 WTO members agreed to expand the Agreement to cover an additional 201 products. Despite the success of the ITA in promoting trade, some WTO members oppose new plurilateral agreements in the belief that their proliferation will undermine the WTO's role as a universal institution, all of whose members acknowledge a common set of obligations and rights.